

1 **Running Title:** PMA qPCR for *E. coli* quantification in irrigation water and fresh
2 lettuce

3

4 **Optimization and validation of a PMA qPCR method for *Escherichia coli***
5 **quantification in primary production**

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12 **ABSTRACT**

13 The microbial requirements defined in many quality assurance guidelines and
14 standards of primary production demand the establishment of microbial sampling
15 programs. Recently, a q-PCR *Escherichia coli* assay has been reported as a good method
16 to quantify the presence of fecal indicator bacterial in groundwater samples. This study
17 focuses on the optimization, validation and application of a qPCR method combined with
18 propidium monoazide (PMA) treatment to exclude DNA from dead cells. A first
19 screening consisting of six primer sets targeting single and multi-copy of *E. coli* were
20 tested to evaluate the sensitivity of the assay. After that, three primer sets were selected,
21 combined with PMA treatment and their capacity to distinguish viable cells when
22 combined with a background of dead cells was assessed. A primer set targeting the 23S
23 rRNA gene was 10-fold more sensitive than the rest of primers, enabling the detection of
24 low concentrations of viable *E. coli* cells. This assay also exhibited good repeatability and
25 reproducibility, which indicates the robustness of the method. Optimized and validated
26 PMA-qPCR was used to enumerate *E. coli* in environmental samples including irrigation
27 water and fresh produce. The results were compared with the levels quantified using
28 qPCR and cultivation-based techniques. Counts of *E. coli* using plate count assay were
29 significantly lower than the levels obtained by molecular techniques (PMA-qPCR and
30 qPCR) in both irrigation water and fresh produce. *E. coli* PMA-qPCR enumeration
31 method showed similar results as qPCR quantification, although the PMA-qPCR
32 treatment seemed to a good alternative to distinguish between viable and dead cells. It
33 can be concluded that that the optimized PMA-qPCR assay can be used by the industry
34 in microbial sampling programs, helping them with the implementation of Good
35 Agricultural Practices (GAP).

36

37 **1. Introduction**

38 A food safety management program focused on primary production is the result of
39 the implementation of available and relevant quality assurance guidelines and standards
40 such as Codex Alimentarius, guidelines on good agricultural practices (GAP), hygiene
41 legislation, and private standards (Kirezieva et al., 2013). In the current European legal
42 framework, microbiological criteria is not defined at the primary production stage, but
43 growers must be able to demonstrate that their operations do not represent a food safety
44 risk (EC, 2004). However, microbiological requirements have been defined in many
45 quality assurance guidelines and standards, which make, the establishment of microbial
46 sampling programs, necessary for growers (Allende & Monaghan, 2015).

47 Traditionally, sampling programs are based on the detection of specific pathogens
48 and the enumeration of indicators of fecal contamination. However, the prohibitive cost
49 and time required for pathogen detection, makes enumeration of microbial indicators a
50 good strategy to characterize microbial contamination in the environment of field
51 cultivation and fresh produce (Park et al., 2013).

52 Indicator microorganisms, such as *Escherichia coli*, are usually used by the industry
53 and competent authorities to assess the implementation of Good Agricultural Practices
54 (GAP). At primary production, *E. coli* have been identified as suitable hygiene criterion
55 in leafy greens as its presence provides evidence of an increased likelihood of potential
56 contamination by ecologically closely related pathogens (Castro-Ibáñez, Gil, Tudela,
57 Ivanek, & Allende, 2015; EFSA, 2014; Holvoet, Sampers, Seynnaeve, Jacxsens &
58 Uyttendaele., 2015). Traditional culture techniques using pour and spread plate count
59 methods are used to enumerate *E. coli* in water and produce samples. However, these
60 cultivation-dependent assays may not represent the most efficient method to predict
61 presence of bacterial pathogens. Ferguson et al., (2013) reported that a qPCR-based *E.*

62 *coli* assay was the best indicator for the presence of bacterial pathogens in groundwater
63 samples.

64 Many studies have focused on the development and optimization of qPCR methods
65 to detect and enumerate *E. coli* in environmental samples as a more sensitive, rapid and
66 specific test than plate counts (Ahmed, Richardson, Sidhu, & Toze, 2012; Ferguson et al.,
67 2013; Pitkänen et al., 2013). However, qPCR-based assays cannot differentiate between
68 viable and dead bacterial cells as DNA of dead cells can persist in the environment, leading
69 to a substantial overestimation of *E. coli* concentrations (Rudi Moen, Drømtorp, & Holck,
70 2005; Varma et al., 2009). To avoid false-positive results, a recently proposed strategy is
71 the treatment of samples with propidium monoazide (PMA) before DNA extraction,
72 allowing the differentiation between viable and dead cells. This technique is based on the
73 ability of PMA to penetrate into the dead cells with compromised membrane integrity and
74 in turn inhibit DNA amplification by PCR following light-induced cross-linking (Nocker,
75 Sossa-Fernandez, Burr & Camper, 2007; Nocker & Camper 2009; Varma et al., 2009;
76 Fittipaldi, Codony, Adrados, Camper & Marotó, 2011). The use of PMA has been
77 successfully integrated with qPCR assays for the differentiation of viable and dead *E. coli*
78 cells in different environmental samples, mostly in water samples (van Frankenhuyzen,
79 Trevors, Flemming, Lee & Habash, 2013; Gensberger et al., 2014; Li et al., 2014; Kim,
80 Gutiérrez-Cacciabue, Schriewer, Rajal, & Wuertz, 2014). However, discrepancies
81 regarding the most recommended primers and PMA concentrations make the selection of
82 a PMA-qPCR method difficult based on the available literature.

83 Environmental samples from the primary production are complex matrices that may
84 interfere with the efficacy of the PMA treatment. Factors such as the ratio between viable
85 and dead bacterial cells, pH and salt concentrations as well as the natural presence of
86 PMA inhibitors have been highlighted as potential inhibitors for the PMA treatment,

87 DNA extraction and qPCR yield (van Frankenhuyzen, Trevors, Lee, Flemming, &
88 Habash, 2011; Fittipaldi, Nocker, & Codony, 2012). Therefore, optimization and
89 validation of previously developed PMA-qPCR methods as well as their suitability as
90 monitoring systems in the primary production are essential before their application as
91 routine tools in microbial sampling programs.

92 Thus, the aim of the present study was the optimization of a previously described
93 PMA-qPCR assay for the quantification of viable generic *E. coli* cells in irrigation water
94 and produce samples covering; (i) selection of specific primer sets for *E. coli* qPCR with
95 TaqMan technology; (ii) characterization of the PMA-qPCR capacity to differentiate
96 between viable and dead cells and (iii) validation of the assay in irrigation water and
97 produce samples taken from a commercial-scale production field of leafy greens.

98

99 **2. Material and methods**

100

101 *2.1. Bacterial strains and inoculum preparation*

102 A seven-strain cocktail of *Escherichia coli* (CECT 434, 471, 515, 516, 533 and
103 LFMFP 679) was used in this study. Strains were obtained from the Spanish Type Culture
104 Collection (CECT) (Valencia, Spain) and the Laboratory of Food Microbiology and Food
105 Preservation (LFMP) (Ghent University, Belgium). Cultures were inoculated in Brain
106 Heart Infusion (BHI) (Scharlau Chemie, Barcelona, Spain) and incubated without
107 agitation at 37°C for 24 h. Then, 2 ml of each strain were combined and washed twice
108 by centrifugation (3500 g, 20 min) at 4 °C in 14 mL of 0.1% buffered peptone water
109 (BPW; AES Chemunex, Marcy l'Etoile, France). The washed cell pellets were suspended
110 in 2 mL of 0.1% BPW.

111

112 2.2. *Sample collection*

113 Water samples were collected at five sampling points from a stream bordering
114 farmlands and urban areas in Murcia (Spain) at six different sampling times. A total
115 volume of 3L was collected using sterile polypropylene plastic bottles. Iceberg lettuces
116 were purchased from a local supermarket at the day of harvest. Samples were transported
117 to the laboratory (within 30 min) and stored at 4 °C for maximum 16 hours until further
118 processing. Lettuce heads, which were confirmed to be free of *E. coli* by Chromocult agar
119 (Oxoid, Hampshire, UK), were sprayed with irrigation water obtained from the urban
120 stream (A) and a mixture of irrigation water and heat-treated irrigation water at a 1:1 ratio
121 (B). Non-sprayed lettuce was used as negative control. After being sprayed with water,
122 lettuce samples were incubated at room temperature for 16 h.

123

124 2.3. *Cultivation-based E. coli quantification*

125 Cultivation-based enumeration of *E. coli* in irrigation water and fresh lettuce
126 samples was performed according to ISO 9308-1:2014. In the case of water samples,
127 different volumes (10 mL and 100 mL) were filtered through 0.45 µm pore size
128 nitrocellulose membranes (Sartorius, Madrid, Spain). For *E. coli* quantification,
129 membranes were aseptically removed from the filter base and placed on Chromocult agar.
130 For iceberg lettuces, external leaves were cut and samples (25 g each) were homogenized
131 for 3 min in 225 mL of 0.1 % BPW using a Stomacher (IUL instruments, Barcelona,
132 Spain). Tenfold dilution series were made in 0.1% BPW and plated onto Chromocult agar.
133 The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h.

134

135 2.4. *Molecular-based E. coli quantification*

136 Water samples were taken from the surface water as previously described. Two 500
137 mL aliquots per sampling point were centrifuged at 3000 g for 20 min and supernatant
138 was removed. In the case of iceberg lettuces, external leaves were cut and three samples
139 (25 g each) were homogenized in 125 ml of sterile 0.1% BPW using a Stomacher at
140 medium speed for 3 min. The homogenate of each sample was divided to obtain two
141 pellets by centrifugation at 3000 g for 10 min. From each water or lettuce sample, one of
142 the pellets was stored at -20 °C for genomic DNA extraction while the other pellet was
143 resuspended in sterile water for PMA treatment.

144

145 2.5. PMA treatment for qPCR

146 Propidium monoazide (PMA) (Biotium Inc, Hayward, CA, USA) was dissolved in
147 20% dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO; (Sigma-Aldrich, Ameresco, USA) as a 20 mM stock
148 solution. Aliquots of 2 mM were transferred to light-impermeable 2 mL microtubes at
149 kept at -20 °C in the dark. For PMA treatment cell suspensions were diluted to a cell
150 density of 10^4 cells/mL in 0.1% BPW. Aliquots of 1 mL of the diluted cell suspensions,
151 irrigation water and lettuce samples were transferred to clear transparent 2-mL
152 microtubes. These aliquots were then centrifuged at 9000 g for 10 min and supernatants
153 removed. Cell pellets were resuspended in 1 ml of sterile water with variable PMA
154 concentrations (10 and 40 μ M). PMA treated microtubes were shaken at 400 rpm for 5
155 min in darkness. The tubes laid on ice were then exposed to a 500-W halogen light source
156 (GE lighting, Cleveland, USA) for 5 min. The distance between microtubes and light
157 source was 20 cm. After light exposure, the bacteria were harvested by centrifugation at
158 9000 g for 10 min.

159 To assay the suitability of PMA to distinguish between viable and dead cells, the
160 above mentioned bacterial cocktail of seven *E. coli* strains was used. The cocktail was

161 divided into two aliquots; one was exposed to 85 °C using a water bath for 15 min to
162 obtain heat-killed bacteria while the other remained as a viable cell suspension. Then, the
163 viable cell suspension was diluted to different concentrations (10^3 , 10^5 and 10^7 cfu/mL)
164 using 0.1% BPW. Cultivation-based enumeration of *E. coli* cells was carried out by
165 plating on plate count agar (PCA; Oxoid, Basingstoke, UK). Viable and heat-killed cell
166 suspensions were mixed to obtain three different mixtures containing ratios of viable:heat
167 killed cells of $10^3:10^7$, $10^5:10^7$ and $10^7:10^7$. Then bacterial suspensions were PMA treated
168 as previously described. After PMA treatment, cells were pelleted at 9000 g for 10 min
169 and stored at -20°C until genomic DNA extraction.

170

171 2.6. DNA extraction

172 DNA from viable, heat-killed and mixed samples of viable and heat-killed cells
173 was isolated using the PrepSEQ™ Rapid Spin sample preparation kit (Applied
174 Biosystems, Madrid, Spain), following the manufacturer's instructions. Genomic DNA
175 isolated from pure cultures was diluted in 100 µl DNase free water. In the case of
176 irrigation water and lettuce samples, genomic DNA was extracted using the MasterPure™
177 Complete DNA and RNA purification kit (Epicenter, Madison, USA) following the
178 manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, pellets were lysed by enzymatic treatment with
179 Proteinase K (50 µg/µL). DNA was precipitated with isopropanol and resuspended in
180 50µL of TE Buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl [pH 7.5], 1 mM EDTA).

181

182 2.7. qPCR procedure

183 Several PCR primers were selected from the published literature. The list of
184 selected primers and TaqMan probes is shown in **Table 1**. The procedure of qPCR was
185 performed using an ABI 7500 Sequence Detection System (ABI, Applied Biosystems,

186 Madrid, Spain). All primers and probes were commercially synthesized by Applied
187 Biosystem. Amplification and detection were carried out in 96-well plates using KAPA
188 PROBE FAST Universal qPCR Master mix kit (KapaBiosystems, Massachusetts, USA).
189 Each reaction was run in triplicate containing 5 μ L of DNA template Final concentrations
190 of primers and probes as well as the applied cycling parameters are listed in **Table 1**. In
191 all cases, a non-template control (NTC) was included using 5 μ L of DNase free water
192 instead of the DNA template. Standard curves were made using known concentrations of
193 genomic DNA isolated from *E. coli* CECT 515T. The *E. coli* concentration in the stock
194 solution was verified by plating on PCA. The reproducibility of the qPCR assays was
195 assessed by determining intra-assay repeatability and inter-assay reproducibility. The
196 coefficient of variation (CV) was calculated using 10-fold serial dilution of genomic DNA
197 isolated from the 7-strain *E. coli* cocktail. The CV was calculated based on the
198 quantification cycle (Cq) value. For the reproducibility, three replicates were made per
199 dilution at the day of experiment and the experiment was repeated on three separate days.
200 To determine the qPCR limit of detection (LOD), standard curves of 10-fold serial
201 dilution of DNA were examined in triplicate. The LOD was determined based on Cq of
202 the last detectable standard. When NTC showed signal in amplification, the calculation
203 of LOD was performed according to the formula $Cq (LOD) = Cq (NTC) - 3$ (Caraguel,
204 Stryhn, Gagné, Dohoo & Hammell, 2011; Gensberger et al., 2014). The samples with Cq
205 values higher than Cq (LOD) were classified as non-determined and Cq values lower
206 were classified as positive. Amplification efficiencies were calculated from the slope of
207 the standard curve as $E = 10^{-1/s} - 1$, where s is the slope of the standard curves (Garrido et
208 al., 2013).

209

210 2.8. *Statistical analysis*

211 Two experimental trials were carried out in independent days and three replicates
212 were analyzed each time (n=9) except for the experiments carried out for the validation
213 of the method in irrigation water and fresh lettuce, where two experiments were done with
214 two replicates (n=6). For calculation and graphical presentation of the median and
215 interquartile range (IQR) of microbial counts only positive samples (i.e., with values
216 above the detection limit) were included. IBM SPSS Statistics 19 was used for statistical
217 analysis. Except when stated otherwise, P values below 0.01 were considered statistically
218 significant. Shapiro-Wilk test was performed to assess the normality of the data (P>0.01).

219

220 **3. Results**

221 *3.1. Primer selection*

222 Primers were selected based on the minimum and maximum C_q obtained from
223 amplification of genomic DNA isolated from viable and heat-killed strains of *E. coli* after
224 treatment with PMA (10 μM) (**Table 2**). Based on the minimum and maximum C_q, the
225 primer sets A, B, D and F, showed the best DNA amplification and good differentiation
226 between viable and heat-killed cells (**Table 2**). The primer set F exhibited the highest
227 sensitivity (LOD 10 cfu) and therefore it was selected for further studies (Figure 1).

228

229 *3.2. qPCR reproducibility*

230 The reaction efficiencies were determined using 10-fold dilutions of genomic DNA
231 isolated from a seven-strain cocktail of *E. coli* treated with PMA. The established
232 detection limit of selected PMA-qPCR assay was determined at -10 cfu/rxn; accordingly
233 the dilution 10⁰ was removed from analysis. Amplification efficiencies were >97%, and
234 correlation coefficient (r²) >0.99 for all qPCR runs. The mean intra-assay and inter-assay
235 CV values were 1.1 ± 0.4% and 3.9 ± 0.7%, which indicates a high reproducibility of the

236 selected method (**Table 3**). The efficiency of the selected qPCR primer set (23F/23R/23P)
237 to detect *E. coli* in water was previously reported by Ahmed et al. (2012). However, until
238 now, the use of this primer set to amplify *E. coli* after PMA treatment has not been studied.

239

240 3.3. PMA-qPCR interference

241 The presence of high concentration of dead cells was evaluated in case it affected
242 the accuracy of the PMA-qPCR method. Viable and heat-killed *E. coli* cells were mixed
243 in different ratios of viable:heat-killed cells of $10^3:10^7$, $10^5:10^7$ and $10^7:10^7$ and treated
244 with PMA before qPCR quantification (**Figure 2**). Viable cells were overestimated in
245 0.2 ± 0.0 , 0.4 ± 0.1 , and 0.1 ± 0.1 log units when 3, 5 and 7 log cfu/mL of viable *E. coli* cells,
246 respectively, were quantified in the presence of 7 log cfu/mL of heat-killed *E. coli* cells.
247 The obtained results indicated that DNA from viable cells was preferably amplified
248 during the PMA-qPCR reaction, which confirms the low interferences between viable
249 and dead cells.

250

251 3.4. Selection of PMA concentration in environmental samples

252 PMA concentration of 10 and 40 μM have been described in the literature as
253 optimal concentrations for inhibiting amplification of DNA from dead cells without
254 affecting the quantification of live *E. coli* cells from different environmental samples
255 (Gensberger, Sessitsch, & Kostic, 2013; Moyle, Harris, & Marco, 2013). Levels of *E. coli*
256 quantified using PMA-qPCR with the two selected PMA concentrations did not show
257 significant differences in irrigation water samples (**Table 4**). Therefore, the lower
258 concentration (10 μM) of PMA was selected for further analysis.

259

260 3.5. PMA qPCR validation in irrigation water and fresh produce.

261 Validation of the selected PMA-qPCR method was carried out in environmental
262 samples of irrigation water and lettuce samples. In irrigation water significant differences
263 in *E. coli* counts determined by cultivation-based method and molecular-based techniques
264 (both qPCR and PMA-qPCR) were observed. In all the cases, counts of cultivable *E. coli*
265 were significantly lower than levels of viable *E. coli* determined by qPCR and PMA-
266 qPCR, approximately 2.28 ± 0.6 and 1.9 ± 0.6 log units, respectively (**Figure 3**).
267 However, no significant differences were observed between the *E. coli* levels quantified
268 by qPCR and PMA-qPCR. The selected PMA-qPCR assay was also validated in fresh
269 lettuce. The median count of *E. coli* enumerated in lettuce samples using cultivation-
270 based assay was 3.23 log cfu/g (IQR 3.3–3.1). *E. coli* levels quantified by PMA-qPCR
271 were significantly higher than those estimated by the plate count method as previously
272 observed for irrigation water (**Figure 4A**). When irrigation water from the urban stream
273 was used, enumeration results of *E. coli* in lettuce samples did not show significant
274 differences between qPCR and PMA-qPCR. However, when iceberg lettuce was sprayed
275 with water containing irrigation water and heat-treated irrigation water, which increased
276 the levels of dead cells, significant differences were observed between the two selected
277 PCR techniques (qPCR and PMA-qPCR) (Figure 4B). DNA isolated from non-irrigated
278 lettuce samples did not show amplification.

279 **4. Discussion**

280 Progressively more growers are requested to implement microbial monitoring
281 programs to comply with the microbial requirements defined in quality assurance
282 guidelines and standards (Uyttendaele et al., 2015). Microbial analyses have been
283 traditionally based in cultivation-based techniques for determination of microbial quality
284 parameters such as *E. coli* (Gensberger et al., 2014). However, recent studies reported
285 that more rapid and specific technologies, such as qPCR, seem to be a more suitable

286 method to evaluate the microbial quality of environmental samples (Ferguson et al.,
287 2013). Some studies have reported PMA-qPCR methods to quantify *E. coli* in
288 environmental samples, predominantly in water (Varma et al., 2009; Gensberger et al.,
289 2013; van Frankenhuyzen et al., 2013; Gensberger et al., 2014; Kim et al., 2014; Li et al.,
290 2014). However, available literature reports the use of different primer sets and PMA
291 concentration, which complicates the selection of the most suitable method. Versatility
292 of the method is also important, making the validation in different sample types, such as
293 irrigation water and fresh produce, necessary. Therefore, this study focused on the
294 evaluation of previously reported PMA-qPCR methods for the enumeration of *E. coli* to
295 select the most suitable one.

296 Many different primer sets have been reported for enumeration of *E. coli* using
297 qPCR (Maheuxa et al., 2009; Chern, Sieftring, Paar, Doolittle & Haugland, 2010;
298 Gensberger et al., 2014). Some authors suggested the utilization of specific marker genes
299 for *E. coli*, the *uidA* gene, which encodes the β -glucuronidase enzyme (Takahashi et al.,
300 2009; Gensberger et al., 2013), while others recommended to target the 23S rRNA, as a
301 more advantageous approach for water samples where numbers of microorganisms are
302 low (Ahmed et al., 2012). Gensberger et al. (2014) reported that the use of the DNA-
303 intercalating dye technology for detecting *E. coli* by RT-PCR showed some difficulties
304 in distinguish clearly and assign melt peaks. In the current study, among the tested sets,
305 two primers targeting the gen *uidA* and one targeting the 23S rRNA gen were preliminary
306 selected because they showed the best Cq values for amplifying viable and heat-killed
307 cells from *E. coli* mixture cultures. However, targeting the sequence encoding in the 23S
308 rRNA gen was 10-fold more sensitive than targeting the *uidA* gene sequence, enabling
309 detection of lower concentrations of viable *E. coli* cells. This effect can be explained by
310 the fact that *uidA* is a single copy gene, whereas average copy number of 23S rRNA genes

311 in *E. coli* is 7 (<https://rrndb.umms.med.umich.edu/>). This primer set also showed a very
312 good repeatability and reproducibility, which indicates the robustness of the method.
313 Although qPCR-based *E. coli* assays have been reported to be more suitable for
314 enumeration of fecal indicator bacteria than cultivation-based techniques (Ferguson et al.,
315 2013), they may overestimate *E. coli* loads due to the DNA amplification from both viable
316 and dead cells (Rudi et al., 2005; Levy-Booth et al., 2007). In the present study,
317 enumeration of *E. coli* concentrations using qPCR assay yielded values around 1.4 orders
318 of magnitude higher than that obtained by cultivation-based techniques. This is in
319 agreement with previously reported results which detected similar differences between
320 the use of qPCR assays and cultivation-based methods due to the quantification of DNA
321 from dead cells (Ahmed et al., 2012; van Frankenhuyzen et al., 2013). Thus, differences
322 observed between qPCR and cultivation-based methods were initially attributed to dead
323 cells, but it could be also due to the presence of viable but none cultivable (VBNC) cells.
324 In fact, the quantification of *E. coli* carried out using qPCR and PMA-qPCR techniques
325 were very similar. Irrigation water is exposed to many environmental factors which might
326 stress the bacterial cells, leading to a loss of bacterial cultivability while viability remains
327 unaltered (Heim, Lleo, Bonato, Guzman, & Canepari, 2002). Turbidity of the water has
328 been reported that might interference with the photoactivation step of PMA, reducing the
329 efficiency of the treatment (van Frankenhuyzen et al., 2011). However, the low turbidity
330 (Nephelometric Turbidity Units (NTU) = 8) of the irrigation water tested in this study
331 makes this hypothesis difficult to sustain as higher NTU values have been reported to
332 interfere with the PMA photocativation (Luo, Lin, & Guo, 2010; Gedalanga & Olson,
333 2009). Therefore, further studies are needed to determine if VBNC organisms play a role
334 in this discrepancy.

335 Some studies demonstrated that viable and dead cell mixtures containing high
336 density of dead cells reduce the performance of PMA treatment (Pan & Breidt, 2007;
337 Løvda, Hovda, Björkblom, & Møller, 2011; Contreras, Urrutia, Sossa, & Nocker, 2011;
338 Elizaquivel, Sánchez, & Aznar, 2012). In fact, PMA differentiation capacity lies
339 approximately in a ratio of viable and dead cells of $10^3:10^7$ (Pan & Breid, 2007; Løvda
340 et al., 2011). This could be partially due to the presence of “ghost” bacteria, which have
341 an intact cell-wall/membrane but are metabolically inactive, leading to the inhibition of
342 PMA effect (Nocker & Camper, 2009). Results obtained in the present study showed that
343 the selected primer set at a PMA concentration of 10 μ M can be used to detect low
344 concentrations of viable *E. coli* cells when mixed with heat-killed bacteria without
345 overestimation.

346 In order to determine the versatility of the selected method to monitor the microbial
347 safety in primary production, enumeration of *E. coli* was carried out in both, irrigation
348 water and produce samples. Results showed that the selected PMA-qPCR methodology
349 was able to detect viable *E. coli* cells in complex matrices, such as irrigation water and
350 lettuce with a mixed background of native microbiota (Rastogi et al., 2012; Staley et al.,
351 2013). In the case of lettuce samples, the number of viable *E. coli* cells quantified by the
352 PMA-qPCR methodology was 2 log units higher than those recovered by cultivation-
353 based techniques. As far as we know, this is the first time that viable *E. coli* cells were
354 detected in irrigation water and on fresh product using the same PMA-qPCR method.

355 Based on the obtained results it can be concluded that the described PMA-qPCR
356 assay represents a suitable technique for the selective detection and quantification of
357 viable *E. coli* cells in irrigation water and produce samples. The use of this methodology
358 may yield a more accurate estimation of *E. coli* loads than traditional cultivation-based
359 methods. This may be a suitable monitoring system to be routinely used by the fresh

360 produce industry for the quantification of indicator microorganisms of fecal
361 contamination, such as *E. coli* without interferences of native microbiota.

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518 **Table 1.** Oligonucleotide primers and probes used in this study (qPCR and PMA-qPCR).

Code	Name	Gen	Sequence (5'-3')	Concentration (nM)	qPCR cycling parameters	Reference
A	784F	uidA	GTGTGATATCTACCCGCTTCGC	900	10 min at 95°C, 40 cycles of 15 s at 95°C, 60 s at 60°C	Frahm et al.,2003
	866R		AGAACGGTTTGTGGTTAATCAGGA	300		
	EC807		(FAM)TCGGCATCCGGTCAGTGGCAGT(TAMRA)	200		
B	ECN1254F	23S rRNA	GCAAGGTGCACGGGAATATT	500	10 min at 95°C, 40 cycles of 15 s at 95°C, 60 s at 62°C	Gensberger et al., 2013
	ECN1328R		CAGGTGATCGGACGCGT	500		
	ECN1277P		(FAM)CGCCACTGGCGGAAGCAACG(TAMRA)	250		
C	rcEC23seq-1728F	23S rRNA	CATAAGCGTCGCTGCCG	1000	10 min at 95°C, 40 cycles of 15 s at 95°C, 60 s at 60°C	Ludwig and Schleifer, 2000
	rcEC23seq-1821R		AAAGAAAGCGTAATAGCTCACTGGTC	1000		
	rcEC23seq-1772T		(FAM)TACATCTTCCGCGCAGGCCGACT(TAMRA)	1000		
D	uid AF	uidA	CAACGAACTGAACTGGCAGA	1000	10 min at 95°C, 40 cycles of 15 s at 95°C, 60 s at 60°C	Chern et al., 2009
	uid AR		CATTACGCTGCGATGGAT	1000		
	uid AP		(FAM)CCCGCCGGAATGGTGATTAC(TAMRA)	800		
E	Ec23Sf	23S rRNA	GAGCCTGAATCAGTGTGTGTG	800	10 min at 95°C, 40 cycles of 30 s at 95°C, 45 s at 55°C	Knappett et al., 2011
	Ec23Sr		ATTTTTGTGTACGGGGCTGT	800		
	EC23Srv1bhq		(FAM)CGCCTTCCAGACGCTTCCAC(BHQ-1)	160		
F	23F	23S rRNA	GGTAGAGCACTGTTTTGGCA	800	10 min at 95°C, 40 cycles of 15 s at 95°C, 60 s at 60°C	Ahmed et al., 2012
	23R		TGTCTCCCGTGATAACTTTCTC	800		
	23P		(FAM)TCATCCCGACTTACCAACCCG (TAMRA)	160		

519

520 **Table 2.** Maximum Cq values obtained for amplification of genomic DNA isolated from
521 a seven-strain *E. coli* cocktail of viable and dead cells (4.4 log cfu/ml) using PMA-qPCR.
522 Each value represents the mean \pm standard deviations of three independent repetitions
523 (n=9).

524

Code	Primer Sets	Viable	Dead
A	784F/866R/EC807	31.5 \pm 2.6	38.5 \pm 1.4
B	ECN 1254F/1328R/1277P	32.0 \pm 2.8	38.8 \pm 0.1
C	EC 1278F/1821R/772T	27.3 \pm 0.0	31.1 \pm 1.4
D	uidA/uidAR/uidAP	31.6 \pm 0.8	39.1 \pm 1.3
E	EC23sF/EC23Sr/EC23Srv1bhq	26.3 \pm 2.9	33.5 \pm 0.2
F	23F/23R/23P	25.2 \pm 0.8	38.2 \pm 0.1

525

526

527 **Table 3.** Coefficient of variation (CV) for the PMA-qPCR assay F (23F/23R/23P;
528 Ahmed et al, 2012) of different dilutions of a seven-strain *E. coli* cocktail. Each value
529 represents the mean of three independent repetitions (n=9).

530

Unit Log	CV (%)	
	Intra-assay	Interassay
5	1.6	4.1
4	1.8	4.4
3	1.0	4.2
2	0.8	4.1
1	0.7	2.7

531

532 **Table 4.** *Escherichia coli* counts in irrigation water using PMA-qPCR when variable
533 concentrations (10 and 40 μ M) of PMA were used.

PMA concentration	<i>E. coli</i> (log cfu/mL)	
	Median	IQR
40 μm	6.4	5.7 – 6.7
10 μm	6.4	5.7 – 6.7
0 μm	6.8	6.2 – 6.8

534

535 **Figures**

536

537 **Figure 1.** Quantification cycle (C_q) values obtained during amplification of different
538 dilutions of a seven-strain *Escherichia coli* cocktail using different primer sets (A:
539 784F/866R/Ec800; B: ECN 1254F/128R/1277P; D: uidAF/uidAR/uidAP; F:
540 23F/23R/23P) for PMA-qPCR enumeration.

541

542 **Figure 2.** *Escherichia coli* counts obtained using the optimized PMA-qPCR assay and
543 cultivation-based techniques (plate count) of a seven-strain *E. coli* cocktail containing
544 variable concentrations of a mixture of viable and heat-killed cells (7 log cfu/mL) and
545 viable cells. Each bar represents the mean \pm standard deviations of three independent
546 repetitions (n=9). Bars labelled with different letters indicate significant difference at P <
547 0.01.

548 **Figure 3.** *Escherichia coli* counts in irrigation water obtained using molecular based
549 techniques (PMA-qPCR and qPCR) and cultivation-based techniques (plate count). Box
550 plot represents three replicates of two independent assays (n=6). The bottom and top of
551 the boxes represent the quartiles (25th and 75th percentile), with the line inside the box
552 representing the median. Whiskers show the greatest values excluding outliers and dots
553 represent outliers (defined as values more than 3/2 times the corresponding quartile).
554 Different letters indicate significant difference at P < 0.01.

555

556 **Figure 4.** *Escherichia coli* counts in lettuce samples after sprayed with irrigation water
557 obtained from the urban stream (A) and a mixture of irrigation water and heat-treated
558 irrigation water at a 1:1 ratio (B) using molecular based techniques (PMA-qPCR and
559 qPCR) and cultivation-based techniques (plate count). Box plot represents three replicates

560 of two independent assays (n=6). The bottom and top of the boxes represent the quartiles
561 (25th and 75th percentile), with the line inside the box representing the median. Whiskers
562 show the greatest values excluding outliers and dots represent outliers (defined as values
563 more than 3/2 times the corresponding quartile). Different letters indicate significant
564 difference at $P < 0.01$.
565

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

